

Reference Architecture for Integrating Computable Smart Contracts with Existing Blockchains

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Abstract—This paper presents a reference architecture designed to integrate computable smart contracts with existing blockchain platforms. The proposed architecture addresses key challenges in the development and deployment of smart contracts, including security, interoperability, and compliance. A central feature of the RA is the introduction of a multichain adapter, which enables seamless deployment of smart contracts across different blockchain environments. By providing a standardized framework, the architecture enhances modularity, accelerates development, and reduces costs while ensuring robust security and regulatory compliance. The main goal of the architecture is facilitating cross-chain deployment and operations of computable smart contracts.

Index Terms—Blockchain; Multichain adapter; Reference architecture; Smart contract.

I. INTRODUCTION

A reference architecture (RA) for computable smart contracts is a cornerstone for researchers and software developers. The RA aims to serve as a blueprint, providing a standardised approach to integrating complex computations with blockchain and distributed ledger technology (DLT). Such an architecture guides developers, product owners, and all relevant stakeholders, ensuring that smart contract [1] solutions are robust, reliable, and aligned with industry best practices and regulatory requirements. The potential benefits are significant, as it overcomes several technical, economic, legal, compliance, and adoption challenges.

Furthermore, the RA is also essential for several reasons.

- **Accelerated development and adoption:** It paves the way for (a) standardisation of a common framework for developer, reducing time-to-develop, (b) incorporating well-established design patterns, security measures, and (c) compatibility between different blockchain platforms and off-chain components. As a result, it encourages a modular development approach for developer, test, maintain, and CI/CD of smart contracts. Such smart contract development architectural framework promotes the use of reusable components and services, speeding up the development process and reducing costs.
- **Mitigating security risks:** It considers well-known vulnerabilities providing resilient guidelines for security risk mitigation. It leads to providing an assurance that the architecture and system components are built on a secure foundation and demonstrates a commitment to open,

secure standards. Trust and transparency establishment becomes easier.

- **Interoperability:** It will facilitate the development of smart contracts that can operate across different blockchain and DLT platforms, reducing redundancy and increasing efficiency while integrating them with existing enterprise systems, promoting smoother and more effective interoperability.
- **Compliance and governance:** It is easier to ensure that smart contracts comply with relevant European (and/or international) regulatory requirements that are crucial for their deployment in finance, healthcare, and other market sectors.
- It allows focusing on **core business logic** development by providing a standardised foundation where business and software developers can collaborate to create their own unique value propositions. Therefore, a reference architecture paves the way for testing out new ideas and services which further encourages the development of novel tools, products, and services that exploit smart contracts.

In addition to the technical benefits, smart contract reference architecture will lead to many business benefits, especially on the front of improved decision making. Having a reference architecture will create a shared and common language and understanding of how smart contracts interact with blockchains at the decision making level of the companies. In terms of cost-benefit analysis when launching a new smart contract product or service, it will enable evaluation of different deployment options based on specific criteria.

Rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II describes the novel reference architecture proposed in this paper. Key considerations and requirements behind developing the reference architecture are also explained. The main novel component of the RA is a multichain adapter which has been detailed along with its purpose. Section III concludes the paper.

II. PROPOSED REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

To ensure that the RA is as comprehensive as possible, following key considerations were taken into account.

- Ensuring the security of contractual data, computations, and smart contract execution is paramount. This includes

implementing data encryption, access control, and secure communication channels to protect sensitive information and maintain system integrity on-chain.

- The off-chain computation environment should be capable of handling increasing computational loads as the system grows. Utilizing load balancing and distributed computing techniques can help achieve this, ensuring that the system remains responsive and efficient under higher demands.
- For the oracle network to be effective, it must be trusted to provide accurate and reliable data. It's essential to have mechanisms in place for verifying the data and computation results, ensuring that the information used in smart contracts is dependable.
- Balancing the cost of off-chain computations with their benefits is crucial. The architecture should be designed to optimize costs without compromising performance, ensuring that the system remains economically viable.
- To maximize flexibility and future-proofing, the architecture should be compatible with various blockchain platforms and off-chain computation environments. This ensures that the system can adapt to different technologies and integrate seamlessly with other systems.

A. Common requirements

The paper also performed an in-depth analysis of smart contract development, execution, and deployment use cases [2]. The analysis leads to deriving common requirements centred on four primary components of the RA.

- **Blockchain network:** This is the underlying distributed ledger technology platform with which the computable smart contract must be integrated and deployed to. The network (e.g., Ethereum, Hyperledger Fabric) thus hosts the smart contract and manages its execution environment.
- **Off-chain computation environment:** This component handles several aspects including any (heavy) computational workload, UI for end users, API gateway, middleware, security, and confidentiality aspects. This environment can be analogous to a cloud based platform, a distributed computing network, or specialised hardware accelerators.
- **Oracle network:** This acts as a bridge between the on-chain and off-chain worlds. It feeds data into the smart contract and relays computation results back to the chain.
- **Data storage:** This component stores the data required for computations. It can be a decentralized storage solution or a centralized database.

The analysis also pointed out the lack of a RA that integrates smart contracts with different blockchain platforms. The current architectures focus on single-platform solutions only and do not address cross-chain and cross-platform integration [3]. For example, Ethereum utilises Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) which instructs how smart contracts are deployed on EVM-compatible chains to ensure they perform uniformly. Hyperledger Fabric on the other hand exploits Chaincode,

which has a different approach than EVM. The reference architecture addresses this gap using a multichain adapter, which is one of the main contributions of the paper.

B. Reference architecture

The proposed reference architecture is depicted below. It comprises of several technical components, which are detailed below.

Fig. 1. Proposed reference architecture for integrating smart contracts into existing blockchains.

- **User Interface (UI) layer:** The UI layer serves as the human-computer interface, enabling users to interact with the smart contract system. It encompasses a web or a mobile app that facilitates end user actions such as initiating computable smart contract agreement, secure transactions, monitoring contract states, and engaging with the underlying blockchain network.
- **API gateway:** It acts as a reverse proxy and a control point. The API Gateway manages inbound and outbound API traffic from a software deployment perspective. Key functions include handling authentication, authorisation, rate limiting, and routing requests to appropriate back-end services. This layer enhances system performance, security, and maintainability.
- **Smart contract layer:** It houses the core logic of the system, comprising self-executing contracts defined in code. This layer is composed of following components:
 - **Smart contract development framework:** It is essentially the software framework where the computation aspects of the contract are handled. It provides tools and libraries for creating, testing, and deploying smart contracts (e.g., Truffle, Hardhat).
 - **Repository:** It is an administrative component which manages versioning and states of smart contracts deployed in the underlying blockchain networks.
 - **Smart contract code:** This module houses the self-executing pieces of code that automate and enforce the terms of contracts (agreed in the UI layer between the contracting parties) without the need for intermediaries.

- **Formal verification:** This module is in charge of evaluating the correctness of the smart contract and its code with respect to a formal specification created smart contract specification module.
- **Blockchain Layer:** the foundation of the overall system, the blockchain layer underpins the execution of smart contracts and recording of transactions. Three essential components of this layer include:
 - **Blockchain network:** The distributed ledger (e.g., Ethereum, Hyperledger Fabric) responsible for maintaining a shared, immutable record of transactions.
 - **Consensus mechanism:** The algorithm ensuring agreement among network participants on the ledger’s state (e.g., Proof of Work, Proof of Stake).
 - **Oracles:** External data providers that bridge the gap between the blockchain and the real world by feeding off-chain information into smart contracts.
- **Middleware layer:** This intermediary layer facilitates communication and integration between the smart contract layer and the blockchain layer. It consists of:
 - **Event listeners:** Monitors blockchain events and triggers corresponding actions within the system.
 - **Off-chain storage interface:** Open interface for web services like storing data external to the blockchain (e.g., in a cloud storage) for optimizing performance and cost.
- **Security services:** It is a set of services covering technical components through authentication, authorization, encryption, and audit/logging mechanisms and is applicable to the entire reference architecture components.
- **Compliance and governance:** Ensuring adherence to legal and regulatory frameworks, this layer includes:
 - **Compliance verification:** This is performing automated checks to validate smart contract alignment with regulations.
 - **Dispute resolution:** It contains the mechanisms for managing conflicts arising from smart contract execution.
- **Multichain adapter for integration and deployment:** While a complex component to develop, this is the main novel aspect of the RA. It consists of three main sub-components. They are elaborated below.
 - **Wrapper class:** It encapsulates common smart contract functionalities (e.g., deployment, calling functions, querying state). It also provides abstract methods for blockchain-specific implementations.
 - **Blockchain specific deployment implementation:** In the second step, it will inherit from the wrapper class and provide concrete implementations for integration and deployment within each blockchain. In addition to that, it handle blockchain-specific micro technical details, such as, transaction building, signing, and sending.
 - **Software configuration:** It is recommended to use

a configuration file to store blockchain-specific parameters and enable dynamic configuration updates.

The multichain adapter contributes with the following novel aspects to the RA. Its abstraction layer defines a common interface or abstract class representing a smart contract and provides software libraries with specific implementations for deploying the computable smart contract to existing blockchains. This allows application and software developers to write the contract once and then execute and deploy it on as many chains as necessary. The wrapper enables using configuration files to store blockchain-specific parameters (network URLs, contract addresses, etc.) which eases the switching between different blockchain environments for deployment. Furthermore, it also utilises dependency management tools to handle blockchain software development kits (SDKs) and other required libraries and natively implements robust error handling mechanisms to gracefully handle exceptions and provide informative error messages. Finally, it is also able to utilise comprehensive unit and integration tests to ensure correctness and exploits testing with blockchain test networks for cost-effective testing.

III. CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, such a well-defined reference architecture provides application and software developers and other blockchain ecosystem stakeholders with a solid foundation for building innovative and scalable applications based on computable smart contracts, enabling them to compete effectively in the digital economy. The proposed reference architecture for integration of computable smart contracts with blockchain and DLTs brings several benefits for the SMEs and the European blockchain ecosystem in terms of reduced developmental cost, offering advanced capabilities, enhanced trust and transparency, and competitive advantages.

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